

Fangs of Snake (Sarpadangstra): A Literary Study

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Abstract

Snakes are the most commonly experienced creature by the human society. There are many incidences of bite by the snakes resulting in a number of problems including death. Snakes bite usually due to (1) fear, (2) being injured, (3) for self protection and (4) to use the substance as food. In all circumstances the main weapon used by the snakes is the fangs (Dangstra). Though not in all situations, when snakes bite, poison is injected through the modified teeth (Fangs that can be closely co-related with Dangstra mentioned in the Ayurvedic classics). A study of the Ayurvedic classics to explore the concept on the fangs is considered by the author important and time tested.

Introduction

Snakes are the creatures dangerous but almost always with the human beings. As per Indian mythology snakes are also the creation that came to existence with the human beings. In some references they are even described as the energy holding the earth. They are said to have immense energy to destroy the creation only with their vision. Basuki, Takshaka etc. are mentioned as the snakes with such energy and capacity to hold and destroy the creation. In common situations they are considered as harmful due to poison. But after many study and observation a number of friendly activities of the snakes towards the human society are also identified.

From experience, research and observations a number of features about the snakes are explored by the humans. A detail study on the morphology, behaviour, reaction towards the external stimuli etc. are being considered as the matters of study by the enthusiastic humans. As the outcome of such enthusiastic studies a number of salient features of the snakes are coming to light. The number, situation, structure, activity etc. of the fangs are some such important points to know about the snakes. The modern scientists explore a number of informations on these points which are interesting and beneficial. But, if looked back to the

ancient health science, Ayurveda, it becomes clear that the scholars and researchers of Indian Health system, Ayurveda, in their samhitas, very clearly discuss detail about the snakes (Sarpa) almost in all respects. They also discuss elaborately about the Fangs (Dangstra) of the snakes that can be considered to be the only weapon to protect from the enemies. Fangs are the weapons of the snakes through which they inject poison to the victim under certain circumstances. Since the present time is of science which needs appropriate evidence hence an effort to explore the ancient concepts on the fangs of snakes (Sarpadangstra) is considered important. The author expects the article to be an eye opener not only for the Ayurvedic scholars but also for the modern scientists to conduct further study and research on the topic.

Materials and Methods

The present study is conducted by following the below mentioned methods using the materials:

(1) Charaka Samhita, Susruta Samhita, Ashtanga Sangraha and Ashtanga Hridaya were studied in the Central Library, Sri Sri College of Ayurvedic Science and Research Hospital, Sri Sri University, Cuttack, Odisha, India.

More Information

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(2) The expressed concepts on the fangs of snake (Sarpadangstra) as mentioned in the mentioned Samhita were found out and collected.

(3) A study of the modern concepts on snake fang was also made using internet as the source.

(4) The Ayurvedic concepts on the topic was tried to justify in Modern light.

(5) Summary, Conclusion and references were added to give the study the form of a scientific article.

(6) The article was then sent for publication to a peer reviewed journal as a gift to the researchers and scientists expecting further study and research.

Results

The study reveals the following facts as the observation and result:

(1) Number and identity of fangs - The snakes are said to have 4 Nos. of Dangstra (Fangs). They are – Bama Adhara (left lower), Bama Uttara (left upper), Dakshina Adhara (right lower) and Dakshina Uttara (right upper). They are said to have specific colors as – Sita (black), Pita (yellow), Rakta (red) and Shyava (Blackish white) respectively [1].

(2) Quantity of poison in the fangs – The quantity of poison in the 4 fangs are prominently mentioned as – Bama Adhara – equal to the quantity of water contained by the hairs of the tail of a cow when it is taken out after submersion into water, Bama Uttara – double, Dakshina Adhara – triple and Dakshina Uttara – 4 times of the quantity contained by the Bama Adhara. Another importance of the color of the 4 fangs is said as that, the bitten part gets the same color of the fang with which the snake bites [1].

(3) Usually during the jyesthamasha (May) the female snake becomes ritumati (prepared to conceive), during Ashada (July) it mates with the male and during Kartika masha (November) lays eggs numbering to 240. From the eggs the birth of male, female and eunuch kids occur [2].

(4) On the 7th day of birth of the kids 4 Dangstra (fangs) appear. The 4 fangs become prepared to inject poison on the 14th day [2].

(5) Color of the fangs – Bama Adhara – Asita (black), Bama Uttara – Pita (yellow), Dakshina Adhara – Rakta (red), Dakshina Uttara – Shyava (blue) [2].

(6) Quantity of poison in the 4 fangs – Bama Adhara – ekabindumatra, Bama Uttara – 2 bindupramana, Dakshina Uttara – 3 bindupramana and Dakshina Adhara – 4 bindupramana. In this context Mudgapramana (green gram) is mentioned as unit [2].

(7) The concept of quantity of poison is related with the hooded snakes only [2].

(8) The snakes bear 44 number of non poisonous teeth also [2].

(9) Poisonous snakes have 2 long sharp fangs. They are hollow and through them the snake injects poison [3].

(10) Snakes typically have between 40-60 teeth. Only the venomous snakes bear fangs [4].

(11) Majority of snakes have over 100 small teeth hidden in the gum divided in many rows. Some snakes like reticulated python bears 50teeth. Snakes with no teeth are colubrids that have no venom [5].

(12) Some snakes like anaconda and pythons have a mouth full of small but very sharp teeth. They have no fang to inject poison [6].

(13) Snakes of Elapidae family (king cobra, cobra and coral snake) may have a couple of teeth, while pythons can have more than 70 teeth [7].

(14) Venomous snakes have 2-4 fangs for injecting poison. The rest are very small teeth used to push food whole down their throat [8].

(15) Viper and cobra are front fanged snakes whereas colubrids are rear-fanged snakes [9].

(16) Fangs are sharp, long, hollow teeth that are hooked up to small sacs in the snake's head behind their eyes [10].

Discussion

The observations of the present study can be discussed as follows:

(1) During the study of the 4 main trustable books of Ayurveda it is observed that, Susruta in Susruta Samhita and Bagbhata in Astangahridaya have not discussed about the fangs of the snakes directly the cause of which is difficult to explain.

(2) Charaka, in Charaka Samhita and Bagbhata, in Astanga Sangraha discuss about the fangs of the snakes. The description of Astanga Sangraha on the topic is more detail and interesting.

(3) Charaka Samhita and Astanga Sangraha unanimously agree that, the number of fangs (Bishadanta- Dangstra) of snake is 4 which has got similarity with some modern opinions.

(4) It is to be agreed that, the description of the 4 poisonous teeth with special reference to color and quantity of poison is interesting and a matter of discussion and research. In the available descriptions such comment is seemed to be unavailable.

(5) In relation to the function of the fangs the same opinion is given by both the Ayurvedic classics and the modern sources. Hence, the depth of study and research of Charaka and Bagbhata (Astanga Sangraha) can be considered to be of far more depth and justification. The description needs more study, research and evaluation. It can be expected that, such studies may explore some interesting hidden facts about the fangs of the snakes.

(6) Concerning to the total number of teeth, though Charaka has given no opinion Bagbhata, in Astanga Sangraha said to be of 44 whereas the modern sources say it to be 40-60, even in some references said to be upto 100. Hence a study on this concern is also seemed to be a demand of the time.

Conclusion

The outcome of the present study can be summarised and concluded as follows:

(1) Ayurvedic scholars, before thousand years of Christ, studied about the snakes with special reference to their morphology, behaviour, their poison and poisonous effects etc. The classics prove the depth and dedication of the scholars.

(2) The great scholar Charaka, in Charaka Samhita and Bagbhata in Astanga Sangraha discuss elaborately about the poisonous teeth (fangs- dangstra) along with other important facts about the snakes.

(3) In Charaka Samhita and Astanga Sangraha the total number of fangs (the modified teeth of the snakes through which poison is injected) is said to be 4. Both the scholars also mention the colour of the 4 fangs. Mentioning of the quantity of poison in the poisonous teeth is an interesting and attention drawing fact.

(4) Total number of teeth of the snake is not mentioned by Charaka but in Astanga Sangraha it is mentioned as 44. Varying from the concept some modern sources say it to be 40 -100.

(5) The descriptions available in Charaka Samhita and Astanga Sangraha have more or less similarity with the modern concepts on the point "SARPADANGSTRA".

(6) A detail, systematic, dedicated study on the Ayurvedic classics to explore the hidden facts on the different concepts may bring out a number of informations that may be proved to be an invaluable boon to the human society.

As conclusion of the study it can be said that, the Ayurvedic scholars, before thousand years of Christ, studied, researched and explored a number of facts related with the nature. Each and every statement available in the Ayurvedic classics has infinite scope of study and research. Dedication and appropriate attention can be considered as the key of success of the researchers.

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Conflict of Interests

Author declares no conflict of interest.

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